

EFFECT OF SPACING AND PINCHING ON YIELD AND ECONOMICS IN AFRICAN MARIGOLD (*Tagetes erecta* L.)V. M. Sonara¹, B. M. Nandre², Yogesh Pawar³, Dhawani Patel⁴ and V. R. Wankhade⁵¹ P.G. student, Department of Floriculture and Landscape Architecture, College of Horticulture, SDAU, Jagudan² Assistant Professor, Department of Horticulture, College of Agriculture, SDAU, Tharad³ Scientist, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, SDAU, Deesa⁴ Assistant Professor, Department of Floriculture and Landscape Architecture, College of Horticulture, SDAU, Jagudan⁵ Assistant Professor, Department of Horticulture, C.P. College of Agriculture, SDAU, Sardarkrushinagarbmnandre@gmail.com

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Abstract

A field trial was carried out to ascertain performance of marigold (cv. Pusa Narangi Gaiinda) during October, 2021 to February, 2022 at College Farm, College of Horticulture, S.D. Agricultural University, Jagudan, Dist. Mehsana, Gujarat. Experiment was comprised of two factors viz., three spacing 60 cm × 30 cm (s_1), 60 cm × 45 cm (s_2) and 45 cm × 45 cm (s_3) and four pinching levels viz., no pinching (p_0), pinching at 25 DAT (p_1), pinching at 40 DAT (p_2) and double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT (p_3). Observations were made and statistically analyzed in Split Plot Design. Treatment s_2 recorded significantly maximum flower yield per plant (380.45 g), whereas s_1 gave highest flower yield per plot (6.78 kg) and per hectare (134.57 q). Among the yield parameters, treatment p_3 recorded significantly maximum flower yield per plant (420.16 g), per plot (6.98 kg) and per hectare (138.57 q). Treatment combination s_2p_3 showed maximum flower yield per plant (530.62 g) while, s_1p_3 gave maximum flower yield per plot (8.19 kg) and per hectare (162.54 q). On the basis of economics s_1p_3 recorded maximum gross return per hectare (Rs. 487626) and net return per hectare (Rs. 354223) with benefit cost ratio i.e., 3.66.

Key words – marigold, two factors, three spacing, four pinching, flower yield.

Introduction

Marigold (*Tagetes erecta* L.) is most commonly grown as loose and cut flower in India is a member of Asteraceae family. It is extensively used in form of garlands for social functions. So far as cultivation of marigold is concerned, the climatic factors are beyond the control of humans but growth and production of marigold can be improved to a large extent by the judicious use of fertilizers, variety, planting time, cultural operations like gap filling, weeding, irrigation, appropriate spacing and pinching etc. Spacing between plants directly regulates plant population per unit area. At wide spacing the individual plant may get sufficient distance for its growth and development. Due to wide spacing per unit area, production is less on the other side; in closer spacing the plants do not get sufficient distance for their development and therefore drastic reduction occurs at close planting. Hence, spacing should be regarded for massing sufficient production of flower yield in African marigold. Pinching treatment might be due to the fact that by removal of apical portion transfer of energy might have been to promote the number of side branches which directly positive correlated the yield of flowers in African marigold. In recent decades there has been increasing in demand of floriculture products with increasing income. Floriculture is an emerging area with great potential both in the domestic as well as export market. In India, commercial floriculture is ongoing development but have a long tradition of various types of flowers. Flowers have been representing in ancient painting, mural and coins. However, the social and economic aspect of flower growing recognized later. It is only in last two three decades (Hawa et al. 2018). Thus, it was desirable to investigate the possibilities of finding out an optimum spacing and pinching to which the plants may have best response. Looking the above facts, the present study was taken up.

Material And Methods

The experiment entitled **Effect of spacing and pinching on yield and economics in African marigold (*Tagetes erecta* L.)** was undertaken during October 2021 to February 2022 at Horticulture Farm, College of Horticulture, Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada University, Jagudan, Dist. Mehsana, Gujarat. This experiment was taken on marigold cv. Pusa Narangi Gaiinda, comprising three factors of spacing viz., 60 cm × 30 cm (s_1), 60 cm × 45 cm (s_2) and 45 cm × 45 cm (s_3) and four levels of pinching viz., no pinching (p_0), pinching at 25 DAT (p_1), pinching at 40 DAT (p_2) and double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT (p_3). Total twelve treatment combinations were tested in Split Plot Design with three replications. The mean data recorded on yield parameters viz. yield per plant (g), yield per plot (kg) and yield per hectare (q) was subjected to statistical analysis following analysis

of variance technique (Panse and Sukhatme, 1985). Economics of each treatment combinations were recorded and discussed.

Results And Discussion**Yield parameters****Effect of spacing (Table 1)**

Maximum flower yield per plant (380.45 g) was found with the s_2 (60 cm × 45 cm), while at s_1 (60 × 30 cm) reported minimum value (320.04 g). This increase in flower yield per plant under widest spacing might be attributed to less competition for food and water among the plants. Similar findings were also noticed by Chauhan and Ambast (2014) in African marigold.

Among the different levels of spacing, s_1 (60 cm × 30 cm) recorded significantly maximum flower yield per plot (6.78 kg) which was at par with the treatment s_3 , whereas s_2 (60 cm × 45 cm) gave minimum value (4.53 kg).

Significantly maximum flower yield per hectare (134.57 q) was recorded with s_1 (60 cm × 30 cm) which was at par with s_3 , whereas minimum value (89.89 q) was observed in s_2 (60 cm × 45 cm). This was due to that numerically a greater number of plants per in to area, which increased the flower yield per hectare (Singh et al. 2018). These results are in conformity with the findings of Ahirwar et al. (2012), Kumar et al. (2012), Chauhan et al. (2014) and Katiyar and Batra (2016).

Effect of pinching (Table 1)

Maximum flower yield per plant (420.94 g) was found in plants pinched at p_3 (double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT) and minimum value (302.90 g) was recorded in p_0 (no pinching) which was highly significant. Flower yield per plant decreased significantly with every decrease in spacing and this might be due to the increased number of branches as well as number of flowers per plant (Kundu et al., 2019). These results are in conformity with the findings of Maharnor et al. (2011) in African marigold.

Among the pinching, significantly maximum flower yield per plot (6.98 kg) was recorded with treatment p_3 (double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT), whereas minimum value (5.16 kg) was recorded with the of treatment p_0 (no pinching). These results are in line with the findings of Jyothi et al. (2018). Significantly maximum flower yield per hectare (138.57 q) was recorded with treatment p_3 (double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT), whereas minimum value (102.31 q) was observed p_0 (no pinching). Similar results are in accordance with Jyothi et al. (2018). This was due to the double pinching treatment which lead to increased number of flowers per plant to ultimately increase the yield per plot and hectare as compare to single pinching and no pinching treatment. These results are in line with the findings of Chauhan and Ambast (2014) and Jyothi et al. (2018) in marigold.

Interaction effect (Table 2)

The Interaction effect between various spacing and pinching treatments was found significant in influencing flower yield per plant. Maximum flower yield per plant (530.62 g) was observed in s₂p₃ (60 cm × 45 cm + double pinching at 25 and 90 DAT) whereas, minimum value (285.10 g) was recorded in s₁p₀. These results are supported by Kour *et al.* (2012) in African marigold.

The interaction between different levels of spacing and pinching also exhibited significant differences on the flower yield per plot where, the maximum yield (8.19 kg) was recorded in s₁p₃ (60 cm × 30 cm + double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT) and minimum value (3.66 kg) was recorded in s₂p₀ (60 cm × 45 cm + no pinching). Among the interactions, maximum flower yield per hectare (162.54 q) was recorded in s₁p₃ (60 cm × 30 cm + double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT), whereas minimum value (72.63 q) was recorded in s₂p₀ (60 cm × 45 cm + no pinching). This might be due to the fact that closest spacing (60 cm × 30 cm) includes higher number of flowers per plot than widest spacing (60 cm × 45 cm) while double pinching gives higher number of flowers as compare to un-pinched plants which have combined effect on higher yield per plot and per hectare in the interaction of double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT and spacing at 60 cm × 45 cm (s₁p₃) and vice versa for s₂p₀ (60 cm × 45 cm + no pinching). These results are in line with the findings of Chauhan and Ambast (2014) and Jyothi *et al.* (2018) in marigold.

Interaction effect of spacing and pinching on economics.

The economics indicating cost of cultivation, gross return, net return and benefit cost ratio under different treatments is furnished in Table 3, 4, 5 and 6.

A perusal of the data regarding economic showed that maximum gross return of Rs. 487626 per ha, net return of Rs. 354223 per ha and benefit cost ratio *i.e.*, 3.66 were recorded with s₁p₃ (60 cm × 30 cm + double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT). Whereas, minimum gross return of Rs. 217895 per ha, net return of Rs. 95383 per ha and benefit cost ratio *i.e.*, 1.78 were recorded with s₂p₀ (60 cm × 45 cm + no pinching).

This might be due to the fact that application of closest spacing of 60 cm × 30 cm and double pinching at 25 and 40 DAT helped in achieving significant flower yield as well as maximum gross and monetary net returns as compared to the other interaction treatments in marigold.

Conclusion

On the basis of the study, it can be concluded that closer spacing and double pinching increases flower yield per unit area, maximizes the net profit per unit area as well as the benefit cost ratio in African marigold cv. Pusa Narangi Gaiinda.

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Table 1: Effect of spacing and pinching on yield parameters

Treatment	Yield		
	Per plant (g)	Per plot (kg)	Per hectare (q)
s ₁	320.04	04.56	90.42
s ₂	380.45	03.06	70.93
s ₃	328.83	04.09	84.14
S.Em ±	004.99	00.18	03.64
C. D. %	019.61	00.72	14.30
C. V. %	005.04	10.85	10.85
p ₀	302.90	03.63	76.08
p ₁	318.02	03.82	80.23
p ₂	330.56	03.71	78.00
p ₃	420.94	04.45	93.01
S.Em ±	015.51	00.22	04.28
C. D. %	046.07	00.64	12.72
C. V. %	013.56	11.04	11.04

Table 2: Interaction effect of spacing and pinching on yield parameters

Treatment Combination	Yield		
	Per plant (g)	Per plot (kg)	Per hectare (q)
s ₁ p ₀	285.10	5.92	117.46
s ₁ p ₁	303.93	6.66	132.14
s ₁ p ₂	301.61	6.36	126.13
s ₁ p ₃	389.51	8.19	162.54
s ₂ p ₀	309.95	3.66	072.63
s ₂ p ₁	334.29	4.09	081.08
s ₂ p ₂	346.92	4.01	079.57
s ₂ p ₃	530.62	6.37	126.29
s ₃ p ₀	313.65	5.89	116.84
s ₃ p ₁	315.84	6.23	123.69
s ₃ p ₂	343.14	6.57	130.40
s ₃ p ₃	342.68	6.39	126.88
S.Em ±	026.86	0.37	007.41
C. D. %	079.80	1.11	022.02
C. V. %	013.56	11.04	011.04

Table 3: Economics as influenced by different treatment combinations

Treatment	Notation	Yield (kg/ha)	Gross Returns (Rs/ha)	Total cost (Rs/ha)	Net Returns (Rs/ha)	Benefit cost ratio
T ₁	s ₁ p ₀	11745.95	352378	128643	223735	2.74
T ₂	s ₁ p ₁	13213.82	396415	131771	264644	3.01
T ₃	s ₁ p ₂	12612.60	378378	133131	245247	2.84
T ₄	s ₁ p ₃	16254.19	487626	133403	354223	3.66
T ₅	s ₂ p ₀	7263.17	217895	122512	95383	1.78
T ₆	s ₂ p ₁	8108.06	243242	122104	121138	1.99
T ₇	s ₂ p ₂	7957.29	238719	123736	114983	1.93
T ₈	s ₂ p ₃	12629.10	378873	124008	254865	3.06
T ₉	s ₃ p ₀	11684.21	350526	127461	223066	2.75
T ₁₀	s ₃ p ₁	12369.03	371071	129229	241842	2.87
T ₁₁	s ₃ p ₂	13039.96	391199	129093	262106	3.03
T ₁₂	s ₃ p ₃	12687.64	380629	130589	250040	2.91

Selling price of marigold: 30 Rs/kg

Table 4: Details of common operational cost of marigold crop

Sr. No.	Particular	Unit	Cost Rs/unit	Quantity	Cost (Rs/ha)
[A] PRE-SOWING OPERATION					
1.	Ploughing (two times)	hrs	600	(2×3) 6	3600
2.	Planking	hrs	600	3	1800
[B] Non-labour input					
1.	FYM (15 t/ha)	Tonne	1000	15	15000
2.	Urea	kg	5.93	543.5	3223
3.	SSP	kg	8.3	625	5188
4.	MOP	kg	18.09	166.7	3015
5.	Irrigation (drip)	hrs	300	30	9000
6.	Transportation	-	300	7	2100
7.	Plant protection	-			10000
[C] Labour input					
1.	Field preparation	Day	340	8	2720
2.	Transplanting	Day	340	10	3400
3.	Fertilizer application	Day	340	10	3400
4.	Gap filling (two times)	Day	340	(3×2) 6	2040
5.	Weeding (three times)	Day	340	(10×3) 30	10200
6.	Application of plant protection	Day	340	7	2380
7.	Earthing up	Day	340	10	3400
Total fixed cost					80465

Note: Rate of various items

Tractor charge @ Rs 600/hr

Labour charge	@	Rs 340/day
Irrigation	@	Rs 300/hr
Transport	@	Rs 300
FYM	@	Rs 1000/t
Urea	@	Rs 5.93/kg
SSP	@	Rs 8.3/kg
MOP	@	Rs 18.09/kg
Seedling cost	@	Rs 0.50/seedling

Table 5: Treatment wise variable cost Rs/ha of supplemented materials

Treatment combinations	Treatment wise variable cost			Total variable cost (Rs/ha)
	Seedling cost (Rs)	Pinching cost (Rs)	Picking cost (Rs)	
s ₁ p ₀	27778	0	20400	48178
s ₁ p ₁	27778	3400	20128	51306
s ₁ p ₂	27778	3400	21488	52666
s ₁ p ₃	27778	6800	18360	52938
s ₂ p ₀	18519	0	23528	42047
s ₂ p ₁	18519	3400	19720	41639
s ₂ p ₂	18519	3400	21352	43271
s ₂ p ₃	18519	6800	18224	43543
s ₃ p ₀	24691	0	22304	46995
s ₃ p ₁	24691	3400	20672	48763
s ₃ p ₂	24691	3400	20536	48627
s ₃ p ₃	24691	6800	18632	50123

Table 6: Details of treatment wise total cost of marigold crop

Treatment combination	Total fixed cost (Rs/ha)	Total variable cost (Rs/ha)	Total cost of cultivation (Rs/ha)
s ₁ p ₀	80465	48178	128643
s ₁ p ₁	80465	51306	131771
s ₁ p ₂	80465	52666	133131
s ₁ p ₃	80465	52938	133403
s ₂ p ₀	80465	42047	122512
s ₂ p ₁	80465	41639	122104
s ₂ p ₂	80465	43271	123736
s ₂ p ₃	80465	43543	124008
s ₃ p ₀	80465	46995	127461
s ₃ p ₁	80465	48763	129229
s ₃ p ₂	80465	48627	129093
s ₃ p ₃	80465	50123	130589